

UDK 528.854.2/ 911.52

SELECTION OF DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL FOR DETERMINING THE HEIGHT AND DEPTH OF LAKES AND PONDS OF THE KHOREZM REGION

Matchanov Otabek Jumanazarovich
PhD student, the Department of Geodesy,
cartography, geography,
Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Urgench State University.
E-mail: otabekj130975@mail.ru

Bekmetova Shoira Hamid qizi
Master student, the Department of Geodesy,
cartography, geography, Faculty of Natural Sciences,
Urgench State University.
E-mail: bekmetovashoira@gmail.com

Аннотасија. So‘nggi yillarda Xorazm viloyatida iqlim o‘zgarishi bilan bog‘liq salbiy holatlar ko‘lami kengaydi. Suv resurslarining tanqisligi oshdi, qurg‘oqchilik muammolari keskinlashdi. Natijada baliqchilik xo‘jaliklarida foydalaniladigan suv havzalari qurib, maydoni qisqarmoqda. Viloyatda iqlim o‘zgarishi ta‘sirini yumshatish va iqlimga moslashish muammolarini o‘rganish mahsadida ko‘l va xovuzlarning chuqurligi, dengiz satxidan balandligi, kollektor va drenaj tarmoqlariga nisbatan joylashuvini o‘rganish lozim. Ushbu tadqiqot ishida Olon ko‘lining dengiz satxidan balandligi bir nechta sun‘iy yo‘ldosh ma‘lumotlari asosida tahlil qilinadi va ko‘l hududida o‘tkazilgan o‘lchash ishlarida olingan natijalar bilan solishtiriladi.

Калит со‘злар: ASTER, SRTM, GTOPO30, ASF, ALOS DSM, ALOS-PALSAR, Google Earth, ArcGIS, raqamli balandlik modeli, ko‘l, xovuz. Google Earth, ArcGIS, рақамли баландлик модели, кўл, ховуз.

Аннотация. В последние годы в Хорезмской области увеличился масштаб неблагоприятных событий, связанных с изменением климата. Обострилась нехватка воды и усугубились проблемы засухи. В результате вода в озерах и прудах, используемых в аквакультуре, иссякает, а площади сокращаются. Для смягчения последствий изменения климата в регионе и изучения проблем адаптации к климату необходимо изучить глубину озер и прудов, их высоту над уровнем моря, их расположение относительно коллекторной и дренажной сетей. В данном исследовании высота озера Олонколь над уровнем моря анализируется на основе нескольких спутниковых данных и сравнивается с результатами, полученными при измерениях, проведенных в районе озера.

Ключевые слова: ASTER, SRTM, GTOPO30, ALOS DSM, ASF, ALOS-PALSAR, Google Earth, ArcGIS, Цифровая модель рельефа, озера, пруд.

Abstract. The scale of adverse events related to climate change has increased in the Khorezm region recent years. Water scarcity has expanded, and drought problems have worsened. As a result, the water of lakes and ponds used in aquaculture has drying up and the area has shrinking. In order to mitigate the effects of climate change in the region and to study the problems of climate adaptation, it is necessary to study the depth of lakes and ponds, their height above sea level, and their location relative to the collector and drainage networks. In this study, the altitude of Olonkul Lake was analyzed on the basis of several satellite data and compared with the results of measurements conducted in the lake area.

Key words: ASTER, SRTM, GTOPO30, ALOS DSM, ASF, ALOS-PALSAR, Google Earth, ArcGIS, DEM, lake, pond.

Introduction: Today, several research institutes offer global digital elevation models (DEMs) to do some research analysis via the internet for free. An appropriate satellite data were selected to determine the elevation of the Khorezm region's lakes above sea level. Digital elevation data obtained from various sources were analyzed by using a geographic information system. The results obtained were compared with field measurements carried out in the area of the lake in order to check the data quality and precision. DEM data, which show the same results as the actual data, will be used as a basis for use in subsequent studies in lakes and ponds in the region.

Literature review: One of the reasons for the stability of lakes is their location: low or high relative to collectors and drains [1]. Several sources provide global digital elevation models that allow researchers to determine the altitude of the surface. Since they are different from each other, it is necessary to identify how they match the real situation or how is their quality. Several researchers have worked to assess the accuracy of ASTER and SRTM data [2, 3, 4]. It says that the reliability level of ASTER GDEM data is 95% and the accuracy level is 17 meters [5]. ASTER is the only satellite that has received altitude data for 99% of the surface area [6]. ALOS (Advanced Land Observing Satellite) DSM is a free digital surface model with a horizontal resolution of 30 meters, which can be used in education, research [7, 8, 9]. Besides, ALOS DSM data is used in a variety of studies such as 3D digital map development, disaster management, damage forecasting, and water resources research [10]. ASF (Alaska Satellite Facility) processes, distributes, and archives satellite data in accordance with NASA's mission. ASF DAAC currently has over a dozen synthetic aperture radar data, choosing high precision for processing from a variety of digital surface models [11, 12]. The accuracy of the ALOS PALSAR DEM provided by ASF is 12.5 meters [13]. A field survey was conducted in the region to determine the accuracy of Google Earth, ASTER, ALOS PALSAR, and SRTM data. In this case, the SRTM data appeared to be more reliable [14]. In this research paper, the height of the lakes is analyzed from six source databases and compared with the field observations.

Study area. The Khorezm region is located between 41⁰ and 42⁰ northern latitudes, 60⁰ and 61⁰ eastern longitudes, in the central part of the Turan lowland, on the territory of the ancient Khorezm-Sarikamysh alluvial delta of the Amu Darya with an area of 6.3 thousand km². The study area is Lake Olonkul with an area of

151.7 hectares, located between $41^{\circ} 39'26''$ - $41^{\circ} 40'39''$ north latitude and $60^{\circ} 08'18''$ - $60^{\circ} 10'11''$ east longitudes, on the territory of the Shavat region (1-figure).

Figure-1. Study area - Lake Olonkul, Shovot district, Khorezm region, Uzbekistan.

Research data and methodology

The Google Earth platform was used to determine the elevation of Lake Olonkul above sea level. Using the TCX Converter and GPS Visualizer (Add elevation), the coordinates of each point on the lake and its elevation above sea level were determined. In this case, the difference between the highest and lowest points above sea level in the lake area was taken as the depth of the lake. Elevation values of the lake were later analyzed based on ArcGIS software through comparing DEM of GTOPO30, ALOS DSM, ALOS-PALSAR, ASTER, and SRTM. According to each data, a bathymetric map was created by determining the altitude of the lake above sea level. Elevation determined data based on each satellite data were compared with the field measurements made in the lake area (Figure 2). DEM data that were closest to on-site measurements are recommended for use in subsequent studies. These data will be used to assess the suitability of lakes and ponds in the region for aquaculture. Surface elevation data is an important indicator for some geography-related research works. Usually, the elevation data of a geographical object are being taken from geographical maps or scientific literature and considered as a simple indicator. And it serves to form a specific geographic imagination of the area where research is carried out. However, the issue of water scarcity highly influences the sustainability of lakes in the region. It means that it is important to determine the location of water bodies above sea level, their position relative to saturation sources, including self-altitude data.

Figure-2. Flowchart of methodology.

Analysis and results

Modern GIS technologies allow rapid and continuous detection of surface elevation data. Free DEM data is one of the possibilities to carry out monitoring. Lake Olonkul, located in Shovot district, was selected to compare and check data precision and accuracy (Figure 3-A). Using Google Earth, the lake area and its surroundings were marked with a line to get elevation (Figure 3-B).

Figure 3. The object of research - Lake Olonkul.

The selected lake area is exported in KML and it was uploaded to TCX Converter. The geographical coordinates of each point marked in the lake area were determined and converted to CSV format. The CSV dimensional data shows the latitude and longitude of each point in the lake but does not provide information on the altitude of the points. Therefore, the data was uploaded to the online GPS Visualizer software and the elevation data of each point was determined. Since the data obtained was in GPX format, it was reloaded into TCX Converter and converted to CSV again. Using this method, geographic coordinates and elevation data are determined for 4211 points marked in and around the lake (Figure 4-A). CSV data was loaded into ArcGIS, and only points within the lake's shoreline were selected using the "Select by Location" command. Using the command "Topo to raster", the data on the height of the lake were converted to raster. Using the "Contour" command, a bathymetric map of the lake was created and the elevation values were displayed (Figure 4-B).

Figure 4. Elevation data of Lake Olonkul determined taken from Google Earth software.

It can be seen that the highest point of the lake was 90 meters above the sea level and the lowest point was 82 meters in the results. These were for Google Earth to determine the elevation data of the lake above sea level. Identifying elevation value by DEM is easier than using Google Earth. Different DEM data were used for this analysis. Firstly, the GTOPO30 data collected from the USGS databases. Then it was entered into ArcGIS. Using the Clip (Data Management) command, the area was cut the overlapping portion of the image with the area of the lakes (Figure 5). As it is clear from the figure, the data on heights were not reflected at all in two of the available lakes (A and C) in the analyzed area. The pixels of GTOPO30 did not fit with the other lakes (V, E, and D). In Olonkul Lake, which we have analyzed, the elevation data (F) is also partially reflected, with the height being 79 meters in all parts of the area. The reason was GTOPO30 data size is large, 30 seconds (approximately 1 km), and this data is not accurate enough to obtain the altitude measurements of small lakes.

Figure 5. GTOPO30 data and overlapping situation in the lake area.

Generally, ASTER special accuracy is higher than the GTOPO30 data, and it is 30 meters worldwide. The same procedure was used for ASTER and SRTM. A bathymetric map of the lake was created, and altitude values were taken. According to ASTER data, the highest point of the lake was 94 meters above sea level and the lowest point was 82 meters (Figure 6-A). It is known that the accuracy of SRTM data is equal to 30 meters. When SRTM data were analyzed in the above method, the highest point of the lake was 89 meters above sea level and the lowest point was 82 meters (Figure 6-B). DEM data provided by the ALOS DSM were analyzed in the same way, the highest point of the lake was 91 meters above sea level and the lowest point was 84 meters (Figure 6-C). Finally, DEM data provided by ALOS-PALSAR were analyzed. The highest point of the lake was 64 meters above sea level and the lowest point was 54 meters (Figure 6-D).

Figure 6. Bathymetric maps of Lake Olonkul, created using ArcGIS, based on ASTER, SRTM, ALOS DSM, ALOS-PALSAR data.

As the data obtained from the above analyzes differed from each other, and varied from the field measurements were carried out in the lake area. The actual height above sea level was measured using GPS at 22 points on the lake (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Field measurement at Olonkul Lake, and points measured by GPS.

The results of the field measurements taken at the lake were compared to get accuracy of DEM sources, and to recommend the suitable ones for further research. Linear correlation analysis was applied. As we know, the correlation analysis is a statistical method used to estimate the strength of a relationship between two quantitative variables. A high correlation means that two or more variables are strongly related to each other, while a weak correlation means that the variables are almost unrelated. Any score from +0.5 to +1 indicates a very strong positive correlation, which means that they both increase at the same time. Conversely, any score from -0.5 to -1 indicates a strong negative correlation, which means that as one variable increases, the other decreases proportionally. Also, a score of 0 indicates that there is no correlation, or relationship, between the two variables [15]. 22 points which measured using GPS in Lake Olonkul, and the corresponding points in 5 DEM data sources were compared (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Results of correlation analysis.

As a result of the comparison, SRTM showed a strong positive correlation with $R^2 = 0.789$. The picture shows that the correlation of ALOS-PALSAR (0.43 points), Google Earth (0.3531 points), ALOS DSM (0.26 points), ASTER (0.007 points) data is low. Besides, the graph in Figure 8 shows that with SRTM data (green line), the actual height (red line) of the lake from the sea level measured using GPS closely overlaps.

Conclusion. Analysis based on data from ASTER, SRTM, GTOPO30, ASF, ALOS DSM, ALOS-PALSAR, Google Earth, and comparison with the results obtained in the field measurements in the lake area showed relatively high accuracy of SRTM data. Therefore, SRTM data have been recommended for further analysis to determine the height of lakes and ponds from the sea level in the Khorezm region.

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